

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF COBALT^{III}. PART I. DIPYRIDINO-COBALTIC bisBIGUANIDIINIUM HYDROXIDE AND ITS SALTS

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Dipyridino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium complex has been prepared by the oxidation of cobaltous bisbiguanidine in presence of pyridine. The dipyridino derivative was found to be more stable than the diamino derivative as it did not hydrolyse. The thiosulphate of this complex, like that of the hydroxo-aquo derivative, changed to μ -thiosulphato-tetrakisbiguanide dithiosulphato-dicobalt. From the complex oxalate, the oxalato-oxalate has been obtained. From the reactions studied the complex was found to have a *trans* configuration. A series of salts, viz., sulphate, nitrate, thiosulphate, iodide, chlorobromide as well as the hydrated base have been prepared and their properties studied.

Diamino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate was prepared by Rây and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 1). It was found to hydrolyse in aqueous solution to hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium complex. The complexes were found to possess a *cis* configuration on the basis of their properties and reactions. The *trans* modification of the series was investigated by Rây and Majumdar (*ibid.*, 1946, 23, 73). The present work was undertaken to ascertain the behaviour of pyridine in the formation of cobaltic bisbiguanidinium complexes.

The dipyridino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium hydroxide was obtained in the same way as that of the diamino complex by the oxidation of the cobaltous bisbiguanidinium hydroxide in presence of pyridine with the help of a brisk current of air. The dipyridino complex was, however, found to be more stable as it did not hydrolyse like the diamino compound. The diamino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate solution on prolonged treatment with air hydrolysed to the hydroxo-aquo complex, but the dipyridino complex remained stable for a long time, and raising the temperature decomposed the complex with the formation of the brownish black cobaltic oxide. Conductivity measurement of the complex nitrate also indicated only slight hydrolysis of the salt.

The behaviour of the dipyridino complex thiosulphate was analogous to that of the hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium thiosulphate as it transformed to the bright, insoluble, green, non-electrolyte binuclear bridge compound, μ -thiosulphato-tetrakisbiguanidinium dithiosulphato-dicobalt, in the presence of a trace of acetic acid or excess of sodium thiosulphate. Unlike the hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium thiosulphate, this reaction with dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium-cobaltic thiosulphate could not be reversed in the presence of alkali.

In the case of a *cis* configuration, an oxalato complex was expected to be formed easily. The cobaltic oxalato-bisbiguanidinium oxalate was, however, obtained as a decomposition product of the complex oxalate at an elevated temperature and in the presence of acid. It is quite possible that under such treatments a change into *cis* configuration first takes place and then the oxalato complex is formed. This indicates a *cis* configuration; probably the original substance is *trans* and is converted into its isomeric

cis form in the presence of H^+ ions. This view is also supported by the failure to easily prepare the oxalato derivative.

Besides the compounds discussed above, the sulphate, nitrate, iodide, hydroxide, chlorohydroxide and chlorobromide of the dipyridino-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium complex have been prepared and their properties studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dipyridino-cobaltic-bisbiguanidinium Hydroxide.—Cobaltous bisbiguanidine was prepared by the action of strongly alkaline (NaOH) biguanide sulphate solution, in calculated quantity, upon a solution of cobalt chloride. It was washed free of alkali with cold water by decantation as rapidly as possible to avoid oxidation. The product was filtered and then treated with pure pyridine and oxidised by passing a brisk current of air through it. After several hours, a red solution with a few red crystals was obtained. There was a slight decomposition of the complex, indicated by the deposition of traces of the black cobalt oxide. The mixture was filtered through a quantitative filter paper. The filtrate on cooling deposited deep violet, permanganate-like crystals. The crystals were filtered out, washed with ice-cold water and alcohol and dried to a constant weight in CO_2 -free air. The substance is soluble in water and reacts alkaline to litmus. {Found: N, 35.60; Co, 12.39. $[Co(Py)_2(BigH^+)_2](OH)_3$, requires N, 35.73; Co, 12.54 per cent}.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium Sulphate.—The red solution of the complex hydroxide on neutralisation with dilute H_2SO_4 deposited red crystals of the sulphate. A minute quantity of the cobaltic trisbiguanidinium sulphate formed was removed by fractional crystallisation from water. Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium sulphate was found to be more soluble. The pure crystals were washed with water and alcohol and dried in air. {Found: N, 24.85; SO_4 , 21.59; Co, 9.00. $[Co(Py)_2(BigH^+)_2](SO_4)_3 \cdot 12 H_2O$, requires N, 25.04; SO_4 , 21.46; Co, 8.80 per cent}. The substance almost completely lost the water of crystallisation at 120° ; but there was a slight decomposition as was apparent from the smell of pyridine.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium Thiosulphate.—The red solution of the complex base was neutralised with dilute HCl. On adding a solution of $Na_2S_2O_3$ dropwise to this solution in the cold, the complex thiosulphate was immediately precipitated as red crystals. The substance was filtered at once, washed with cold water and alcohol and dried in air. {Found: Co, 9.28; S_2O_3 , 26.30. $[Co(Py)_2(BigH^+)_2](S_2O_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, requires Co, 9.20; S_2O_3 , 26.21 per cent}.

When, however, an excess of $Na_2S_2O_3$ was used a green precipitate was obtained. The red thiosulphate slowly changed to the insoluble bright green variety in the presence of a trace of acetic acid also. The green product was washed with water and alcohol and dried in air. It did not contain any pyridine. {Found: Co, 13.23; S_2O_3 , 37.68. $[Co_2(S_2O_3)_3(BigH^+)_4]$ requires Co, 13.18; S_2O_3 , 37.58 per cent}. This compound was the μ -thiosulphato-tetrakisbiguanidinium dithiosulphato-dicobalt, originally prepared by Rây and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 7).

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium nitrate was precipitated as deep violet crystals when the base was neutralised with dilute HNO₃. The crystals were filtered with ice-cold water and alcohol, in which it was slightly soluble, and dried in air. The substance is readily soluble in water. {Found: Co, 9.85; NO₃, 31.63. [Co(Py)₂(BigH⁺)₂](NO₃)₂ requires Co, 9.73; NO₃, 30.75 per cent}.

Equivalent conductivity of [Co(Py)₂(BigH⁺)₂](NO₃)₂ at 35° ± .2.

Dilution (litres)	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Ω_v	113.37	120.32	128.77	142.59	146.33	151.24
Ω_{oc} (mean)	156.29					

$(1 + n_1 \times n_2 \cdot 0.692 \cdot v)^{-1}$ where n_1 and n_2 are the valences of the cation and the anion.

In case of [Co(NH₃)₂(BigH⁺)₂] Cl₂·2H₂O the value for Ω_{1024} was found to be 178.8 mohs at 33° (Rây and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*). The complex was found to hydrolyse to a large degree.

The equivalent conductivity of this salt can be compared with that of La(NO₃)₃ at 25° (Landolt, Tabellen, 1923, II, p. 1090).

v (litres)	32	64*	128	256	512	1024
Ω_v	104.8	112.0	119.9	125.5	130.9	134.5

From this it can be inferred that the dipyridino complex hydrolyses to a very small degree in aqueous solution.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium iodide was prepared by the action of a concentrated solution of KI on that of the complex nitrate. The crystals separated on cooling in scarlet-red colour. The substance was recrystallised from water, washed with alcohol and dried in air. {Found: Co, 7.13; I, 45.30. [Co(Py)₂(BigH⁺)₂](I)₂·2H₂O requires Co, 7.05; I, 45.46 per cent}. The substance is readily soluble in water and alcohol.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium Chlorohydroxide.—The solution of the complex base, when partly neutralised (p_n 8.9) with dilute HCl, furnished a violet precipitate. This was washed thoroughly with water and alcohol and dried to a constant weight in CO₂-free air. {Found: Co, 12.25; Cl, 7.00. [Co(Py)₂(BigH⁺)₂](OH)₂Cl $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires Co, 11.86; Cl, 7.13 per cent}. The violet precipitate obtained at p_n 8.9 dissolved on adding more HCl to a clear violet solution, forming probably the normal chloride; but this could not be isolated in a pure state due to high solubility.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium monochlorobromide was obtained by completely neutralising the complex base and then adding a strong solution of KBr. At first a few crops of orange-yellow cobaltic trisbiguanidinium bromide were obtained and finally after standing for two days in cold the chlorobromide separated as red-violet long needles. The crystals were purified by recrystallisation from water and washed and dried as usual. {Found: Co, 9.1; total Ag halide, 78.25. [Co(Py)₂(BigH⁺)₂](ClBr)₂·2H₂O requires Co, 9.01; total Ag halide, 79.8 per cent}.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-bisbiguanidinium oxalate was prepared by neutralising the complex base with oxalic acid. The red crystals were filtered, washed with water and alcohol and dried in air. {Found: Co, 9.61; C_2O_4 , 20.30. $[Co(Py)_2(BigH^+)_2](C_2O_4)_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ requires Co, 9.46; C_2O_4 , 21.10 per cent}. The substance on heating at 95° decomposed with the loss of water and pyridine. It is soluble in water. The solution on heating slowly evolves pyridine and the colour changes to violet.

Cobaltic-dipyridino-oxalato-bisbiguanidinium Oxalate.—A solution of the complex oxalate was heated at about 60° in presence of a little of H_2SO_4 . The colour of the solution gradually changed from red to violet and pyridine was disengaged; when the evolution of pyridine ceased the solution was cooled and deep violet crystals separated. These were filtered, washed and dried in the usual way. {Found: Co, 13.90; N, 31.9; C_2O_4 , 29.4. $[Co(C_2O_4)(BigH^+)_2](C_2O_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Co, 13.95; N, 32.6; C_2O_4 , 30.77 per cent}. This compound was also obtained from the hydroxo-aquo-cobaltic-bisbiguanidinium hydroxide hydrate by Rây and Majumdar (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 82). The compound is sparingly soluble in water. The compound could not be prepared by the action of excess of $Na_2C_2O_4$ on a hot solution of the normal oxalate. The complex decomposed giving a blue solution.

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